

Teachers Attitudes towards Technology integration: A Gender-Based study in Secondary Schools

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Abstract

The paradigm shift in teaching-learning is prominent over the past few years with the inclusion of technology in classroom. The use of information and communication technology in education is not confined to optimize and enhance the classroom learning but also to acquaint them with 21st century skills. In such case, the role of teacher becomes significant for the smooth transaction of knowledge with the use of assistive technology. The present study seeks to comprehend the attitude of secondary schools' teachers towards the technological integration in the teaching learning process. The study also explored the gender difference in attitude towards the use of technology in the classroom. Descriptive survey method was adopted in the present study as it aims to explore the current status of phenomenon. A self-constructed tool with 5- point Likert scale was used to collect the data from 52 secondary school teachers from the Udalguri district of Assam, of which 27 were male and 25 were female teachers. Statistical analysis like Mean, Standard deviation, Percentage were used to interpret the level of attitude towards technological integration in teaching- learning, including t-test to determine the gender-based difference in the attitude. The study highlights the significance of teacher's attitude towards the use of assistive technology in teaching- learning process, which implicitly indicates their efficiency to integrate such aids in the classroom.

Keywords

Teachers Attitudes, Technology Integration, Gender Differences, Resources, Digital Experience.

Introduction

Today, science and technology has invaded in every sphere of human life. Knowledge explosion is taking place at a rapid pace in every field emerging new things in the technological world. Everyday something new is coming up and there is a need to get acquainted with rapid changes taking place in the world of technology. Today technology is considered as an important part of life and an integral component of education. The significant transformation of technology integration in education makes the teaching learning process more effective and tremendous beneficial changes in this discipline has been occurred. The concept of the importance of technology integration in the field of education has been developed significantly from the last decade. Integrating technology into teacher training is no longer optional; it is essential for preparing educators to meet the demands of contemporary teaching and learning environments (M. K. Jena, & Dr. S. K. Pandey, 2024). "Effective integration of technology is achieved when students are able to select technology tool to help them obtain information in a timely manner, analyze and synthesize the information, and present it professionally. The technology should become an integral part of how the classroom functions-as accessible as all other classroom tools" (National Educational Technology Standard for Students, ISTE). "Technology integration is the process of teaching technology (technology education) and another curricular area simultaneously. In addition, it is the process of using technology to enhance teaching for learning (Educational technology)"- EdTech Connect.

Technology today has become an essential part of the educational process, but is rarely it is integrated into a student's learning experience in the classroom. Integrating technology into a classroom means more than simply teaching basic computer skills and software programs. Effective technology integration must be there across the curriculum in ways that will enhance the learning process for students.

Attitudes is a predispositions or determining tendencies to respond in a specified manner. It involves directions as well as magnitudes. When a person shows some tendencies to approach an objects, it is said to be the positive attitude towards it and when he shows a tendency to avoid the object, his attitude is describe as

negative. Both these attitude may involve intense feelings and vary from large negative values to increasingly positive (Mangal, S.K. 2013). Teacher's attitudes towards technology integration are inclined by different variables like demographic variables, professional factor (Beri & Sharma, 2019) institutional variables – infrastructures and technical support and psychological factor like self-efficacy and perception and other contextual factor like curriculum, peer collaboration etc. From earlier research, it is found that teacher's attitudes towards using digital tools and its integration are positively inclined with adequate training, supportive institutional policies and access to resources and lack of these variables often leads to resistance of technology integration.

Significance of the study

The secondary education is a very crucial stage in which the students tries to adopt themselves to solve multitudinous problems through technology integration along with academic acquisition. Technology integration in this stage is very significant as it bridges up the gap between the foundational learning and the further education for future adaptability. The students generally at this stage highly motivated and responds towards the learning through technology driven learning instead of traditional rote method. Besides it, use of digital tools, interactive content and multi-media resources makes their learning more engaging. Secondary education is the stepping stone to higher education and employment and the teacher plays the role of facilitator by developing communication and collaboration skills for higher education through the digital tools and online platform that encourages digital literacy. It also encourages the student's inclusive learning environment as well as the flexibility of education and enable them to move within and across education to enhance their employability and fulfil the needs. In short, technology integration equips the students of secondary school with proper knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to thrive in a digital and competitive world in 21st century. It not only makes learning interactive and accessible but also prepares them for higher education, careers, and life-long learning.

Objective of study

Following objectives are formed for the present study

1. To examine the attitudes of secondary school teachers towards technology integration in their teaching practices.
2. To study the differences in teachers' attitudes towards technology integration on the basis of gender.
3. To study the differences in teachers' attitudes towards technology integration on the basis of age group.

Review of Literature

Albert, P. (2016) Studied on Higher secondary teachers' attitudes towards the use of ICT in the teaching-learning process. The researcher found that the higher secondary teachers have neutral attitude towards using new technology in teaching. Male and female teachers differ significantly in their attitude towards using new technology. Government and private school teachers do not differ significantly in their attitude towards using new technology.

Nimisha Beri, Lalit Sharma (2019) on Teachers' Attitude towards Integrating ICT in Teacher Education. The study examined the attitudes of teacher educators in Haryana, India, towards using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in their teaching. The research found that while teacher-educators generally have a positive attitude towards ICT, they may lack training, technical support, and motivation to fully integrate it into the education process. The authors conclude that ICT training, technical support, resources, and motivational factors are important for successful ICT integration in teacher education.

Kaur, M. (2019) on the role of teachers' attitude and beliefs regarding use of ICT in Indian classrooms, the study clearly shows that Indian school teachers have positive attitude and beliefs towards use of ICT in classrooms. This study do not support any gender differences in use of ICT as male and female teachers are at equal position in use of ICT. The research also reported that use of ICT in Indian school teaching is inadequate and insufficient.

Erkan A. (2019) studied to investigate the teachers and students views on using technology and its effect communication/interaction and found that the choice of educational technology is related to teachers' perception which is communication/interaction with the student can be enhanced using technology. The study examines the factors or the impact of using technology between teacher-student communication/interaction in Turkey.

Sarita, G. (2020) investigated the attitudes of secondary school teachers in Meerut city towards information and communication technology (ICT). The study

employed a descriptive cum survey method with a sample of 120 teachers randomly selected from government and private secondary schools. Results indicated that teachers generally hold a favorable attitude towards ICT, and no significant differences were found based on gender, subject stream, or school area.

Reena Rani and Anisha (2023) investigated on ICT Enhanced Instruction in Mathematics Sprucing up Students' Achievement published in the Indian Journal of Educational Technology. The finding of the research indicates that students who had learned Geometry content by using ICT-enabled programmes were significantly better in their Mathematics achievement as compared to students who underwent traditional learning.

Anupama, V., & Grace, C. I. (2024) conducted a research work on the perceptions of teachers towards the application of computers in the teaching-learning process and the findings revealed that 21% of teachers have high perceptions, 55% have average perceptions, and 24% have low perceptions regarding the use of computers in the teaching-learning process. The availability of support and resources was perceived as the most significant factor, followed by the usefulness for students, the impact of Information Technology, teachers' interest and acceptance, and productivity for teaching. Significant differences were observed in perceptions based on gender, with male teachers showing more positive attitudes compared to female teachers. Urban teachers exhibited more favorable perceptions than rural teachers.

The reviewed studies collectively highlights the favourable and positive attitudes of the teachers towards ICT integration in the teaching- learning process. In the study of Reena Rani and Anisha (2023) and Sarita, G. (2020), a positive impact of ICT enabled instruction helps student's achievement and improves teacher-students interaction. On the other hand, Albert,P. (2016) found that teachers attitudes differs by gender whereas Kaur, M. (2019) and Sarita.G (2020) founds no significant differences in the study.

Main Text

Operational key terms

Technology integration Technology integration refers to effective use of technology tools with specific purpose to support and enhance teaching learning process in the classroom. It is simply perceives as the replacement of traditional methods of teaching in the school and involves with the use of digital devices,software and online resources to facilitate learning experiences that are more interactive, personalized and aligned with specific learning objectives.

Attitude An attitude is an enduring system that include a cognitive component, a feeling component and an action tendency. It involves beliefs as well as evaluation of an individual. It is a psychological construct, a mental and emotional entity that characterizes positive and negative predisposition towards any person, objects or events.

Secondary School Teacher The teachers who teaches secondary or higher secondary school that includes classes from VI to XII.

Hypothesis

Hypothesis of Study:

1. There is no significant differences in teacher's attitude towards technology integration in secondary schools with regard to gender.
2. There is no significant differences in teacher's attitude towards technology integration in secondary schools with regard to age group

Methodology

The descriptive survey method was adopted to carry out the study to examine the attitudes of secondary school teachers toward the integration of technology in teaching and learning. The design was chosen because it enables the collection of quantitative data from a large population and allows for comparison across gender.

Population and sample In the present study, all the teachers of secondary schools of Udalguri district constitute the population. Purposive sampling technique was adopted in the selection of sample school. A total number of 52 secondary school teachers were taken consisting 25 male and 27 female for the study from 10 no's of schools by using simple random sampling. Technique.

Tools Used

A self-structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data on the attitudes of secondary school teachers to examine the technological integration in teaching learning process. Data are collected by using 5 point Likert scale. A 5-point Likert scale is one of the most commonly used tools in surveys and research to measure people's attitudes, opinions, or perceptions.

Analysis

Statistical analysis

1. Based on the collected data, following statistics have been used in the study -

2. Descriptive statistics like Frequency distribution, Mean, Standard deviation and standard Error of Mean.
3. Inferential statistics like t-test is used to compare the mean attitude scores between male and female teachers.
4. Analysis of Variance to compare the age group of the group.

Analysis of the study

Objective 1: To examine the attitudes of secondary school teachers towards technology integration in their teaching practices.

Table -1 Level of Attitudes of secondary School Teachers towards Technology Integration

Interval (Likert Category)	Total (n=52)	% of Total
11–18 (Strongly Disagree)	0	0%
19–26 (Disagree)	1	1.92%
27–34 (Neutral)	2	3.84%
35–42 (Agree)	35	67.30%
43–50 (Strongly Agree)	14	26.92%
Total	52	100%

Interpretation:

In the table no 1, the level of attitudes of 52 secondary school teachers towards technology integration are presented. From the table 1, it is found that only 26.92% of the secondary school teachers are strongly endorsed technology integration, showing with positive attitude but teachers may still be cautious in giving their highest approval. Again 67.30%, a large majority of teachers agreed that technology integration is beneficial for secondary school students. It denotes a positive inclination towards digital tools in teaching. 3.84% teachers are in neutral position means that these teachers are neither strongly supported nor opposed the technology use in the classroom which reflects a lack of confidence, training or other exposure. A few teachers i.e. 1.92% of teachers shows disagreement which reflects that negative attitude is very rare and none of the shows strongly disagreed which means there is no extreme resistance towards technology integration. In short, it is found that a large number of secondary school teachers have positive outlook on technology integration but a significant number remain neutral highlighting the importance of institutional support and professional development to boost confidence and promote effective use of it.

The figure -1 shows the levels of teacher’s attitudes of secondary school towards technology integration.

Attitudes of Teacher towards Technology Integration

Objective 2: To study the differences in teachers' attitudes towards technology integration on the basis of gender.

Ho1: There is no significant difference in teacher's attitudes toward technology integration in secondary schools with regard to gender.

Table -2 Percentage Distribution of Attitude scores of Male and Female Teachers

Interval (Likert Category)	Male (n=27)	Male %	Female (n=25)	Female %	Total (n=52)	% of Total
10–18 (Strongly Disagree)	0	0	0	0	0	0%
19–26 (Disagree)	0	0	1	4	1	1.92%
27–34 (Neutral)	0	0	2	8	2	3.84%
35–42 (Agree)	19	70.37	16	64	35	67.30
43–50 (Strongly Agree)	8	29.63	6	24	14	26.92
Total	27	100	25	100	52	100

Interpretation:

From the Table No-2, it has been seen that the percentage of strongly agreed male teacher is 29.63% (8) whereas female teacher is 24 % (6). Again the percentage of male response of agree level is 70.37% (19) while female possesses 64% (16) which indicates a positive attitude towards adopting technology with less gender differences. About 8% female and 0% male teacher's remains neutral which means both the group highlights the need for further awareness and professional development. On the other hand, in the level of disagree, none of the male teacher are found and only a single female teacher disagreed. Again, in the strongly disagree level, neither the male teacher nor the female teacher strongly disagreed with the technology integration. The table is shown in the Figure -2.

*3 (Attitude score of male and female teachers towards technology integration – make correct in the box)

Figure- 2 clearly shows percentage distribution of Attitude scores of both Male and Female teachers.

Table 3 t-value of Attitude Scores of Teachers towards Technology Integration

Variables	Category	N	M	SD	Std. Error of Mean	t-test
Secondary School Teachers Attitude	Male	27	42.9	5.43	1.58	0.87
	Female	25	41.53	5.97		

Interpretation and Testing Hypotheses

From Table- 3, it has been found that the value of Mean is 42.9 and SD is 5.43 in case of Male teachers. Again, in case of Female teachers the Mean is 41.53 and SD is 5.97 respectively. The t-value is found 0.87 which is not significant at both level (5% and 1%) of levels of significance as the table value is 1.96 at 5% and 2.58 at 1% levels of significance. Therefore, from the above results, it can be clearly interpreted that there is no significant difference between the attitudes of male and female teachers towards the technology integration in secondary school and the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference in teacher's attitudes toward technology integration in secondary schools with regard to gender" can be accepted.

Objective: 3 -To study the differences in teachers' attitudes towards technology integration on the basis of age group.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in teachers' attitudes toward technology integration with regard to age groups.

Table - 3 Teachers Attitudes Score across the age group

Groups	Scores	N	M	SD
Below 30	37,44,40, 43, 42, 47, 40, 43, 47	9	42.56	3.29
31 -40	40, 40, 40, 40, 40, 36, 48, 21, 38, 36, 39, 45, 33, 37	14	38.07	6.12
41-50	38, 42, 40, 36, 43, 34, 36, 40, 36, 45, 40, 40, 45, 40, 39, 35, 43	17	39.52	3.38
51 and above	41, 38, 38, 36, 38, 45, 40, 40, 43, 37, 40, 46	12	40.17	3.13
Total		52	39.81	4.39

Table – 4 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between Groups	113.02	3	37.67	2.08	0.115
Within Groups	869.05	48	18.11		
Total	982.08	51			

Interpretation

A one way of ANOVA is conducted to compare the teacher's attitudes towards the technology integration across the age group of the teacher. From the Table No. 4, it is found that the calculated value is 2.08 and the tabulated value of F is 2.84 and 4.31 respectively at both levels of significance (5% and 1%) with degree of freedom V1= 3 and V2= 48. As our calculated value of F= 2.08 is less than the table value at both level of significance, and hence our hypothesis cannot be rejected. Although the mean scores vary slightly, these differences are not large enough to be statistically significant. The analysis reveals that the teacher's attitudes score do not differ significantly based on age group. Therefore, it can be concluded that the age of the teacher is not a determining factor in the attitudes towards the technology integration in the study.

Result and Discussion

The findings of the present study revealed positive attitude of teachers towards the inclusion of technology in teaching- learning process regardless of gender. Majority of teachers perceived the inclusion of digital tools enhances classroom efficiency. However, a chunk of population disagreed and displayed neutral stance

to the integration of any kind of digital aids in the classroom. This may be the result of different factors that come in play in the classroom scenario. The use of technological aids in teaching- learning process predominantly during Covid-19 pandemic further highlighted the urgency of technological integration in classroom. The only medium of communication for teaching- learning during Covid-19 pandemic was digital platforms that required different set of skills. To be precise pandemic played a significant role in changing the educational landscape of India. However, the change came with its advantages and limitations. Teacher who was well equipped with new age technology had advantage compared to teachers who were not. The findings of this study showed chunk of teachers who showed neutral response to the integration of technology in education portrays perplexity of teachers in modern classrooms. This leads to think for curriculum reformation in teacher training institutions to prepare prospective teachers with skills required for new age classrooms.

The findings with regard to gender contradicted with the study conducted by Kumar et al. (2023) that showed difference in opinion between male and female teachers towards the use of ICT in classroom. However, the present study revealed that there is no significant difference in attitude of male and female teachers towards technology integration. The considerable number of female teachers revealed that technology integration is essential for teaching-learning efficient, interesting and lively. Other factors that play significant role is age, the findings revealed teachers below 30 years highlighted favorable attitude, whereas teachers at their 30s and above revealed lack of enthusiasm towards the use technology in classroom.

Findings

1. About 26.92% teachers strongly agreed to the need of technology integration in the classroom.
2. Majority (67.30%) of teachers showed positive attitude towards the integration of technology in the teaching-learning process.
3. About 3.84% teachers showed neutral position and very few (1.92%) disagreed to the statement.
4. In case of gender, no significant difference was perceived, prominent number of both male and female teachers showed favorable attitude towards the inclusion of technology in classroom
5. Majority of male teachers (70.37%) agreed that technology is essential, while 29.63% showed desirable attitude and none of the teachers were found neutral, disagree or strongly disagree level.
6. Similarly, in case of female teachers, 24% strongly agreed, considerable number (64%) highlighted the need of technology inclusion to enhance classroom efficiency. However, 8% teachers showed neutral stance and 4% disagreed the technology integration.
7. t-test revealed that there is no significant difference in the attitudes of male and female teachers on technology integration.
8. The results of the ANOVA analysis showed no statistically significant difference across the age group of the teachers.
9. The age group (under 30) demonstrated average attitude, while the scores of teachers between 31- 40 years portrayed lowest score, but not prominent enough to be statistically significant.
10. The overall mean scores (39.81) and SD (4.39) demonstrated the moderate positive attitudes towards the technology integration.

Conclusion

In the present study, it is reflected that the attitudes of teacher play a crucial role in the effective technology integration in secondary school which leads to highest benefit to the students. Although the findings revealed the absence of gender-based differences, yet sometimes their attitudes vary in degree and orientation which impact in enhancing teaching and learning in the classroom. It is also seen from the previous studies that gender-based differences are not always statistically significant, but it provides insights into how personal beliefs, confidence and exposure with digital tools can influence acceptance and use of technology in education. Therefore, for the effective use of digital tools for technology integration in education, the teachers should be provided supportive school environment, develop proper infrastructure, promoting equitable access to resource materials, proper training and timely incentives to develop positive attitude towards digital pedagogy. So the investigator feels that fostering inclusive and supportive approaches of technology integration in the classroom can enhance the teaching learning process and equips the students to meet the demands of the 21st century.

Limitation of the Study

De-limitation of study:

The present study is delimited in the following way:

The study is delimited to secondary school teachers of provincialized junior and senior

secondary schools of Udalguri district.

Teachers of Secondary schools under SEBA and Assam Higher secondary Education Council.

The study is delimited to secondary schools of Udalguri District of Assam only.

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